

PREVENTING DIABETES ON A BUDGET

Eating healthy is crucial for overall well-being, as poor nutrition is linked to chronic diseases like heart disease, diabetes, and obesity, which affect millions of Americans. According to the CDC, heart disease is the leading cause of death in the U.S., with poor diet being a major risk factor, and over 37 million Americans have diabetes, many cases being preventable through healthy eating. A balanced diet rich in fruits, vegetables, and whole foods can help reduce these risks, improve energy levels, and support long-term health. Money should not keep you from being healthy and disease free!

Find more information on the American Diabetes Association website here!

SOME TIPS & TRICKS:

01. WEEKLY MEAL PREP

Plan your meals for the week and write a grocery list to help you not buy things you don't need.

02. BUY IN BULK & USE STORE BRANDS

You can save money by buying staple foods like rice, beans, and oats in bulk. Although store-brand items are less expensive than name-brand ones, they are frequently just as nutrient-dense.

03. USE COUPONS & SHOP THE SALE ITEMS

To save money on necessities, look through grocery store flyers, use coupons, and take advantage of senior discounts at participating businesses.

04. COOK MEALS AT HOME

Compared to pre-packaged or restaurant meals, home-cooked meals are typically healthier and less expensive. Time and money can also be saved by freezing portions and cooking in batches.

05. CHOOSE NUTRIENT DENSE FOODS

To get the most nutrition for your money, choose inexpensive, nutrient-dense foods like eggs, canned tuna, frozen veggies, legumes, and whole grains.

A map of the United States with the text "37 million diagnoses" overlaid on it, indicating the prevalence of diabetes in the country.

37 million diagnoses